

GAS ASSISTED WHOLE-FIELD PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENT FOR LIQUID COMPOSITE MOLDING PROCESSES

Ben Wang^{1*}, Gaurav Garg¹, Chuck Zhang¹, Zhiyong Liang¹ and Chiang Shih²

¹*Department of Industrial Engineering*

²*Department of Mechanical Engineering*

*Florida A&M University-Florida State University College of Engineering
2525 Pottsdamer Street, Tallahassee, FL 32310-6046*

ABSTRACT: For liquid composite molding, the quality of the final parts is dependent upon the quality and uniformity of the fiber preform. Permeability is commonly used to indicate the properties of the fiber preforms. However, conventional permeability measurement methods, which use liquid (oil or resin) as working fluid, only measure the average preform permeability in an off-line mode. This method cannot create an in-situ permeability profile due to fiber pollution or used to reveal a preform's local permeability variations. This paper introduces a new permeability characterization method using gas flow to detect and measure preform permeability variations in a closed mold assembly prior to resin injection. GRASP (Gas assisted Real-time ASessment of Permeability), is based upon two research findings: (1) resin permeability correlates well with air permeability for the same fiber preform with well-controlled gas flow, and (2) the whole-field air permeability profile of a preform can be obtained through measuring gas flow pressure. In this study, the validity of the gas-assisted, in-situ permeability measurement technique was established and proven effective by qualitatively detecting non-uniformities and permeability variations in various fiber preforms. A two-dimensional flow model was developed to quantitatively estimate the whole-field preform permeability profile using predetermined pressure distribution. The efficacy of the new method was illustrated through several test cases. This new method can be used as a tool for in-situ measurement and monitoring of preform permeability for process design and quality control.

KEY WORDS: Resin Transfer Molding, Preforms, Flow Modeling

INTRODUCTION

Liquid composite molding (LCM), such as resin transfer molding (RTM) or vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM), has become a popular composite processing technique due to its wide applications in many industries, particularly aerospace and automotive industries. The reason for this popularity is its ability to manufacture high performance composite structures of complex shapes with relatively low cost. However, some technical difficulties still exist in LCM processes. One major problem associated with LCM manufacturing is part reproducibility. The majority of the RTM quality problems are caused by the variation of preform permeability as a result of poor raw materials, improper preform loading and poor mold-fit.

Most of the research work so far in the field of measuring fiber preform permeability focused on measuring average permeability. Fiber permeability is typically measured using specially designed molds. Using Darcy's Law, measurements of pressure, flow rate or flow distance of the fluid are used to calculate an average permeability for the fiber material. These techniques measure permeability off-line and cannot be used to reveal preform's local permeability

variations. Because actual fiber preforms are flexible and unsteady structures, which can be easily deformed during handling and loading, theoretical measurements of permeability are often inaccurate. In the field of composite process modeling/simulation, current research mainly focuses on developing process models/algorithms predicting actual manufacturing behaviors [1-3]. These models require information on the permeability of the preform. The accuracy of the simulation results are related to the accuracy of the preform permeability profile used for simulation. Therefore, permeability characterization has become an important part of the process, which has been studied by various researchers during the last decade [4-11]. The research includes the investigation of the permeability of various fiber structures. These research studies provide a fundamental understanding of permeability through analytical and experimental investigations. A permeability database for standard reference fabrics was also developed [7].

In this study, the authors further developed and tested the Gas assisted Real-time Assessment of Permeability (GRASP) technique, based on an earlier study [12]. In that study, the authors established the validity of a gas-assisted, in-situ permeability measurement technique, demonstrating that this measurement and analysis technique was effective in detecting non-uniformities and permeability variations in fiber preforms. The authors demonstrated that the whole-field permeability profile of the preform in the mold could be estimated using a gas (e.g. N₂) as the flow medium. They also showed that when the gas flow is well controlled, the resin permeability is highly correlated with the gas permeability. Therefore, the whole-field permeability profile of the preform in the mold can be characterized with the gas before resin injection. The effectiveness of this approach lies in the fact that estimating permeability distribution with a gas flow is far cheaper and easier compared to using a resin-based method. Also, this gas-based approach is in-situ and with a resin-based system, we can measure permeability only in an offline mode. In this study, the authors further improved the experimental setup and numerical models for the GRASP technique.

GRASP TESTBED SETUP

This study presents further work on the same system as used in a previous study [12]. The main difference is that the system has been refined since then, and now we can make pressure measurements from all the pressure transducers simultaneously. Also, the data acquisition is implemented using the LabVIEW software. The gas-assisted permeability measurement testbed consists of the following components:

- A mold with constant planar dimensions and depth (Figure 1);
- Low-pressure measuring transducers;
- A circuit board that houses the 54 transducers (Figure 1);
- A flow meter for measuring the gas flow;
- LabVIEW data acquisition software with appropriate instrumentation (Figure 3);
- A high-pressure supply source of nitrogen gas.

The rectangular mold cavity is 22.86cm long by 15.4cm wide and 0.635cm deep. The mold is made of aluminum and consists of two parts, the bottom mold cavity, which is fitted with O-ring groove, and the top cover with the aligned pins. At the inlet and outlet, the test fluid flows through a narrow gap 1.27cm wide. More information on the mold design can be found from the earlier study [12]. Figure 2 shows the fiber placement location and actual measurement area with respect to the mold cavity.

National Instruments' SCXI modules were integrated with LabVIEW software to facilitate the data collection process. A circuit board, which houses all the 54 pressure transducers, was

produced. The box provides power to all the transducers and eradicates all the interference effects. A data acquisition program graphically displays the pressure and permeability information. Figure 4 shows the user interface of the program. The data from all the 54 pressure transducers were collected and then processed/analyzed using the Tecplot plotting software. The collected transducer output data is an average of 500 samples, collected at a frequency of 1000 samples/sec.

Figure 1: The mold and circuit board with 54 transducers

Figure 2: Mold cavity and the fiber placement

Figure 3: The LabVIEW data acquisition program with real-time pressure and permeability profiles displayed

EXPERIMENTS

Although the methodology and validation of the experiments were discussed in detail in the previous study [12], a brief review is provided here. Under conditions that do not violate Darcy's Law, permeability should remain constant and determined solely by the size, shape and orientation of the pores in the porous media, regardless of physical properties of the flowing fluid. In a previous study by the authors [12], it was demonstrated that the experimental conditions were in accordance with those required to satisfy Darcy's Law. They made use of the Reynolds number to show that the flow in the experiments was laminar and that the compressible and inertial effects can be neglected.

In this study, four cases with different fiber contents and arrangements were tested. The layout of the fibers in the mold cavity for different cases is shown in Figure 4. The cases include: Case 1:

uniform case (Figure 4(a)); Case 2: Central more fiber case (Figure 4(b)); Case 3: central less fiber case (Figure 4(c)) and Case 4: edge effect case (Figure 4(d)).

Figure 4: Experimental cases

The preforms used in the tests were 0/90 balanced knitted E-glass fabrics (COFAB A118, CollinsCraft Composites Inc., Walhalla, SC). In Case 1, 13 layers of fibers were loaded in the mold cavity. Case 1 served as the base for comparing the other test cases. The mold construction and the pressure sensors used in this study were described in detail by the authors in reference [12]. The fiber volume content (V_f) was found to be about 50%. In Case 2, referred to as the central more layer case, 3 layers of smaller size fiber were inserted between 10 layers of full size fiber mats. The permeability variation between the two regions was found to be about 55% as reported in an earlier study [13]. Case 3, referred to as the central less layer case, consisted of 13 fiber layers (as in Case 1) but holes were cut into 3 of the 13 layers to reduce the fiber volume content in the mold. The holes in the 3 layers aligned with each other. Since the fiber volume content was less in the region where the holes were made, the permeability was expected to be high compared to the rest of the mold. This variation was reported to be about 217% [13]. Case 4 also had the 13 layers but 6 of the layers were cut short of their width. The objective was to study the edge effect of a preform. In all the plots presented in this study, the horizontal axis was aligned with the flow direction and flow was always left to right.

NUMERICAL ESTIMATION OF WHOLE-FIELD PERMEABILITY PROFILE

A C++ code was written to numerically calculate the permeability profile of the preform in the mold. The program uses the finite difference method. The numerical calculation was based on mass balance and Darcy's Law. The permeability of fiber perform is governed by Darcy's Law for flow of a viscous fluid through an anisotropic, homogenous, porous medium. The Darcy's Law is given by:

$$V_i = -\frac{K_{ij}}{\mu} \cdot \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_j}$$

where μ is the dynamic viscosity; $\partial p/\partial x_j$ are the pressure gradients along x_j direction; and K_{ij} is the permeability tensor. After introducing the stream function ψ , and making some basic mathematical manipulations, the final finite difference form is expressed as:

$$\frac{\psi_C - \psi_D}{dx} + \frac{\psi_B - \psi_A}{dx} \cdot \frac{P_C - P_D}{dx} + \frac{P_B - P_A}{dx} + \frac{\psi_D - \psi_A}{dy} + \frac{\psi_C - \psi_B}{dy} \cdot \frac{P_D - P_A}{dy} + \frac{P_C - P_B}{dy} = 0$$

To validate the code, it was first tested for cases with predetermined permeability distributions. The pressure distributions in a two dimensional mold were obtained using a finite element analysis-based RTM simulation software [12].

Certain information is required for using the RTM simulation software:

- Geometry of the mold cavity;
- Gate and vent locations;
- Porosity of the fiber and viscosity of the fluid;
- Permeability and directional properties of the fiber perform; and
- Flow rate (constant flow rate condition) or inlet pressure (constant pressure condition)

The flow medium was the nitrogen gas in the test cases. With the given inputs, the software provided the pressure distribution in the mold and the filling time.

In Case 2, with two regions of fibers with different fiber content and hence different permeability, the inlet conditions were specified and the mesh structure was chosen. The pressure distribution obtained by the software is shown in Figure 5(a). The flow was from left to right and hence the left boundary (inlet) had a larger pressure than the right boundary (outlet). The flow inlet condition was prescribed as 270 Pa. All the nodes at the left boundary were chosen as inlet. Similarly, all the nodes on the right boundary were chosen as outlets. The plot shows that the flow came to atmospheric condition at the outlet (pressure is zero on right boundary).

Figure 5: Numerical estimation of permeability from simulated pressure (Case 2)

The region enclosed by dashed lines represents the region with more fiber content and hence lower permeability. The permeability values input to the two regions were $2.71\text{E}-10\text{m}^2$ for the lower permeability region (K_1^0) and $9.23\text{E}-10\text{m}^2$ for the remainder of the mold cavity (K_2^0). The region outside the mold was given the same permeability value since in actual situation would have the same fiber content. The software was run under constant pressure conditions at the inlet. The other choice was to run with constant flow conditions at the inlet. The researchers speculated that for the flow using gas as the fluid medium, a significant difference in the two conditions would not result. When using gas as the flow medium, the fiber preform was instantly saturated and the saturated flow conditions were instantly achieved. When a liquid like Silicone Oil is used as the flow medium, the fibers were slowly saturated depending on the forcing pressure. If a constant flow has to be maintained, then the forcing pressure must be increased with time, and if a constant pressure condition is maintained, then the flow rate of the fluid decreases as the flow front traverses. Therefore, unlike liquid flow, the constant flow and constant pressure conditions

would be similar when using gas as the flow medium. We measured flow rate and inlet pressure condition in the experiments.

A total of 143 mesh nodes were used in a plane for calculating the pressure distribution, 13 in Y direction and 11 in X direction. The software took longer as the number of nodes increased. The pressure data obtained from the RTM software was fed to the permeability calculation program. Other parameters, like size of the mold, flow rate, viscosity of the fluid and porosity of fiber were specified within the permeability calculation program.

The permeability profile for Case 2 using the C program was plotted and is shown in Figure 5(b). The figure distinctly shows two discrete regions of permeability. The first shows the region of low permeability ($K_1=2.21E-10m^2$) enclosed entirely by the dashed lines. With respect to the X and Y -axis, the location of the region inside the dashed line loop coincides exactly to the location of the dashed line loop shown in Figure 5(a). This is the region of low permeability that was specified in the software program for determining the pressure distribution. The location and size of the region matches exactly with what was specified in the software. However, the permeability values are a little different. The specified value was $K_1^0=2.71E-10m^2$ but the calculated value is $K_1=2.21E-10m^2$. This difference could be due to the different parameters used in the calculating the permeability in the two cases. While the software program providing the pressure distribution uses the inlet pressure of the gas as the input, the permeability calculation program uses the flow rate of the gas. Since neither the total pressure nor the velocity of the gas was known, matching the conditions exactly was difficult. A constant pressure condition was used in the software to match the conditions with an earlier study [12]. The numerically computed permeability value for the outer region was found to be $K_2=7.35E-10m^2$, while the value specified to the software was $K_2^0=9.23E-10m^2$. Although differences in the permeability values were found, the numerical program nevertheless provides a good qualitative estimation of the permeability that matches well with the permeability profile given to the software.

Case 3 was used to evaluate the permeability calculation program. Figure 6(a) shows the pressure distribution obtained from the RTM simulation software. Again, the flow is from left to right. The flow inlet condition was prescribed as 270 Pa. All the nodes at the left boundary were chosen as inlet. Similarly, all the nodes on the right boundary were chosen as outlets.

Figure 6: Numerical estimation of permeability from simulated pressure (Case 3)

The area enclosed by dashed lines represents the region with less fiber content and hence higher permeability. The permeability values input to the two regions were $K_1^0=2.76E-09m^2$ for the higher permeability region and $K_2^0=9.23E-10m^2$ for the remainder of the mold. The software was run with constant pressure conditions at the inlet.

The pressure data obtained from the RTM simulation software used to compute permeability for Case 3 is shown in Figure 6(b). Like in Case 2 (Figure 5(b)), for Case 3 (Figure 6(b)) two distinct regions of permeability contours can be seen. The region within the dashed line loop is the region with higher permeability and the outer region has lower permeability. The size and location of the region with lower permeability matches exactly with the region of lower permeability as inputted in the software. As in Case 2, a difference between the specified and computed values of permeability also appeared in Case 3. The specified value was $K_1^0=2.76E-09m^2$ and $K_2^0=9.23E-10m^2$ and the numerically computed values for the regions is $K_1=1.33E-09m^2$ and $K_2=4.46E-10m^2$, respectively. However, unlike in Case 2, the transition between the two regions was smooth. The spacing between the contour lines and number of lines indicates that the transition is not as sharp as in Case 2. This is a direct reflection of the pressure distribution shown in Figure 6(b). Though within the region of higher permeability, regions of differing permeability (contour lines) can be seen. The difference between these differing values is insignificant compared to the difference in permeability between higher and lower permeability regions.

These results indicate that the program to compute permeability from a given pressure distribution works satisfactorily. The utility of the program was verified using studies for Case 2 and Case 3. The results for the two cases indicate that the program can identify the regions of different permeability with exact location and size, which indicates that the program is able to effectively estimate permeability from the pressure profile obtained by the RTM software. We will make extensive use of the numerical model in our analysis of the permeability for different cases.

Figures 7 and 8 show the pressure and the numerically calculated permeability profiles for Case 2 and Case 3, respectively. Figure 7(a) shows the experimental pressure profile for Case 2. The rectangular region enclosed by the dashed line represents the spatial region of high fiber volume. As expected, the pressure contour lines are denser in the region of high fiber content. The permeability profile for the corresponding pressure profile is shown in Figure 7(b). The region within the dashed rectangle is the region of low permeability value and matches well spatially with the actual fiber placement.

Figure 7: Numerical estimation of permeability from simulated pressure (Case 2)

Although the fiber volume content in the mold cavity has only two distinct values, a continuous distribution of permeability values that can be seen in Figure 7(b). Another feature visible in the permeability plot is the presence of negative permeability values. Although the number of

negative permeability values is not significant, their presence nonetheless warrants attention. Steps are being taken to address this issue.

Figure 8: Numerical estimation of permeability from simulated pressure (Case 3)

Experimental pressure profile and permeability profile for Case 3 are shown in Figure 8(a) and 8(b), respectively. The holes in the fiber mats were located in a different region than the center of the measurement region (indicated by the dashed line rectangle). The corresponding region in the permeability profile is a region of high permeability surrounded by the region of low permeability. Negative permeability values were present as shown in Figure 8(b). Although the negative numbers were very few, steps are being taken to address this issue.

3D MOLD EXPERIMENTS

A 3D mold with complex geometry was designed and manufactured to extend the scope of the work and better understand the method. Figure 9 shows the design of the mold.

Figure 9: The 3D Mold; (a) male mold piece (b) female mold piece

Figure 9(a) shows the male piece of the mold. The mold cavity dimensions were 80mm x 110mm x 24mm. The design was chosen to provide an asymmetric greater understanding of the flow pattern. The edges on one side of the male piece were made sharp and on the opposite side made smooth to introduce asymmetry. The male piece was manufactured of a 12.27mm thick transparent Plexiglas sheet. The transparent material was chosen to facilitate the visualization experiments at a later stage. Figure 9(b) shows the female piece of the mold, which was made of the thick steel block. A total of 168 pressure ports were drilled on 5 surfaces of the female mold for pressure measurements (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Female mold piece with plastic fittings

The 3D mold was tested for several cases. The same experimental hardware was used for the experiments as in the planar mold. The LabVIEW data acquisition program was modified to suit the changed test condition. Since the circuit board can handle data from only 54 pressure ports at a time, the experiments for the 3D mold required at least two runs per test case. The fiber used for the preliminary study was 0/90 balanced knitted E-glass fabrics, which is same as the one used for the planar mold.

Figure 11: Pressure profile for the 3D mold (gas inlet pressure = 5 kPa)

Figure 11 illustrates the preliminary results for Case 3 experiments on the 3D mold. The mold was filled with 8 layers of fiber among which 3 layers had circular holes in the central area. The dashed region in Figure 11(a) indicates the size and location of the holes in the fiber.

For the test case, the experiment was performed with the gas inlet pressure maintained at 5kPa. The plot in Figure 11(a) presents the pressure profile with 5kPa inlet pressure. The divergence of pressure contour lines in the dashed circular region is obvious, indicating a higher permeability area in the central area. The quantitative permeability profile calculated using the finite difference method (Figure 11(b)) also illustrates the higher permeability in the central area of the preform. Currently, the finite difference based permeability estimation code is preliminary and can only handle simple 3D geometry with constant thickness (such as the part in Figure 9). Studies are ongoing to develop numerical algorithms to estimate permeability for complex 3D geometry from measured pressures.

CONCLUSION

A new permeability characterization method was developed and tested (the technique has been patented (US Pat. #: 6532799)). This method uses the pressure profile of the gas in the mold to numerically calculate the whole-field permeability profile. This concept can be very effective in measuring the preform permeability variation in a closed mold assembly before the liquid resin injection. The pressure data is acquired from all the points simultaneously. The graphical display enables visualizing both the pressure and the permeability field in the mold cavity before the resin injection. Suitable corrections or modifications can be made in the fiber preform to manufacture defect-free composite parts. The technique was initially tested with a planar mold and later applied to a 3D mold with encouraging results. Several cases of fiber preform layouts were discussed. More experimental and numerical investigations are ongoing to further improve this new method. The method could provide a more practical technical solution to quality control problems for the RTM and other LCM processes.

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